

METHODOLOGY OF FORMING BILINGUISTIC COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS IN PRIVATE EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

Amirkulov A.

Teacher, MK ACADEMY

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***Abstract.** Today, formation and development of bilingual competence of students of private educational institutions is of great importance. The article highlights the issues of language education in bilingual harmony.*

***Keywords:** foreign language, opportunity, bilingual, vision, hearing, memory, technology, essence, mentality, culture.*

In modern society, the problem of mutual understanding of different cultures, linguistic and cultural diversity of the peoples of the world, and relations between different ethnic communities is becoming urgent. Globalization imposes on teachers the task of forming globally oriented individuals who understand and value different cultures based on human values, are ready for intercultural communication and live in mutual understanding with representatives of other nations in the modern world.

Today, formation and development of bilingual competence of students of private educational institutions is of great importance. That is, it is necessary to familiarize students not only with the language of the country, the culture of the studied nation, but also with their daily life and customs. Acquiring this competence provides an understanding of the similarities and differences in the life of the nation in which one lives and whose language is studied. To achieve this, first of all, one of the main tasks of the teacher is to motivate students, that is, to form an understanding of the necessity, possibility and convenience of learning Uzbek language and foreign languages. In this context, it is desirable to conduct language education in bilingual harmony. The educational purpose of teaching a foreign language is manifested in the following. The essence of this purpose is to provide children with ideological education, inculcate intellectual skills, and increase their cognitive activity. The educational goal is mainly realized in two ways:

1) directly in a foreign language, greeting, saying goodbye, knowing the names of objects and events, reciting poems and songs, playing games, etc., are very interesting tasks for children, especially in the initial training;

2) to be able to relate to each other within the framework of etiquette during communication, to be able to interpret their actions, the information obtained from audio text and graphic texts is of incomparable educational value.

The educational value of extracurricular activities is also unlimited.

The developmental goal of foreign language education includes the following. It is consistent with the meaning of developmental education in didactics and represents the development of mental, emotional and motivational aspects of child's personality. The child receives intellectual and spiritual nourishment, tests his feelings in speech communication, learns the opinion of interlocutors (child, teacher, announcer, etc.) and expresses his own opinion.

In the foreign language teaching methodology, the realization of the goal of general education envisages the assimilation of useful vital information and new simple information about the language through the studied language tool. Overcoming normal linguistic and speech difficulties in the educational process, including learning foreign languages, ensures the development of the child's thinking and emotions. The developmental goal is achieved only through speech acts. Its serious difference from the general educational purpose is that education is connected with the acquisition of educational information, the content of information serves to form various competencies.

When a language learner sees, hears, and uses a word in his or her speech, the chances of memorizing and mastering it are high. The use of new pedagogical technology methods in the educational system shows good effect in achieving such results. Currently, the study of foreign languages is given great importance in our republic. For our nation, which is building its great future, the importance of perfect knowledge of foreign languages is huge. Any language in the world is considered a common phenomenon in terms of its place in society, its function and its true nature.

But at the same time, since there are more than three thousand languages in the world, each of them is a unique world of rules. Because each language is always created according to people's living conditions and mentality. From this point of view, globalization, that is, as a result of the development of science and technology of the whole world, international relations create the need for a single common language. In particular, the increasing influence of the United States and foreign countries on the world economy, politics and culture naturally causes the influence and reputation of a foreign language to increase. Therefore, new words and terms are being learned in private educational institutions in harmony with the spirit of the times. Countries striving for the heights of modern science, technology are trying to master English language and use it for their own benefit. In this regard, our republic is not an exception, because it is necessary to develop, enrich and improve our national language in order to be equal to other languages. In the process of learning a foreign language, readers and students always try to compare the structure of the foreign language they are learning with their native language, as well as scientifically based research and classify the features of both languages, such as the construction of phonological, morphological, syntactic and lexical layers. In short, in order to enrich our language and introduce our identity to the peoples of the world, we can rely on Uzbek language and English, the most common among international languages.

The concept of bilingual competence is translated from Latin as "bilingual", "bilingualism". Bilingual education system works in Scandinavian countries, Great Britain, Switzerland, Canada, USA and others. Bilingualism can be defined as a prerequisite for effective interactions and relationships between languages and cultures. Intercultural competence implements social interaction in terms of the implementation of multicultural education ideas in modern society.

Bilingualism is a concept that describes the subject's knowledge of two languages when both languages are used in communication. At the same time, the level of knowledge of the second language should be sufficient to exchange ideas in this language. Bilingual education includes multicultural education and bilingual education in terms of wide exposure of a person to world culture. Bilingual education is the interaction between the teacher and students in the process of learning subjects through the mother tongue and foreign languages, as well as ensuring a high level of knowledge of a foreign language, assimilation of the content of professional, intercultural and

linguistic competences related to science. Subject-related professional competences reflect the uniqueness of educational subjects studied in bilingual mode and determine the level of mastery of educational content. Intercultural competence is related to the ability of students to carry out social interactions in modern society in terms of the practical implementation of multicultural educational ideas.

The level of professional skills among students is directly related to the level of mastery of this special knowledge. But it is impossible to talk about intercultural communication as a generalization with a living carrier of language and national culture in the educational process. In specially organized teaching conditions, the foreign language teacher is sometimes the only communicative partner of the students.

But this does not mean that there is no intercultural knowledge and communication in foreign language classes. Dialogue of cultures can be carried out when students interact with teachers, educational materials (printed, audio, visual linguistic data sources) and in internal communication of students, in the process of thinking, in the process of knowing and understanding language phenomena.

Methodology of formation of bilingual competence of students in private educational institutions assumes several types of bilingualism. Depending on the age:

- From an early age (early simultaneous bilingualism) - the child learns both languages before the age of 3-4 years.

- Early sequential bilingualism (early sequential bilingualism) - the child first acquires the mother tongue, and then learns the second language until adolescence.

- Late (late sequential bilingualism) – adults learn a second language purposefully.

Depending on the level of mastery:

- Balanced (coordinate/balanced bilingualism) - if both languages are at a high level. This type of bilingualism involves perceiving each language as a separate system, in which concepts and grammatical structures do not intersect with the other.

- Unbalanced (subordinate/unbalanced bilingualism) - one develops better than the other. Usually, such bilingualism develops in adults who have moved to another country, and their native language is manifested in the form of exchange in speech.

- Compound bilingualism - language systems are mixed with each other, and a person cannot always know which language's grammar and vocabulary he is currently using. This is often found in early bilingualism.

However, bilingualism does not require perfect knowledge of both languages. It is important to know each of them to the required degree: on one level, for example, to be able to speak fluently, and on the second level, it is important to be able to read well.

In private educational institutions, in particular, in the formation of bilingual competence of students of schools where education is conducted in Russian and other languages, more attention is paid to the lexical-speech topic during Uzbek language classes. We can also include words of praise and prayer in the vocabulary.

Teaching about applause and prayers, which are the national values of Uzbek people, can be included in the textbooks of schools conducted in Russian and other languages, such as dictation, which not only increases children's grammatical knowledge, but also stabilizes mutual respect and closeness to Uzbek people through Uzbek language.

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